

JADIDS AND JADID PRESS AS THE TRIBUNE OF CALLING FOR NATIONAL AWAKENING

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Annotation: The article is mainly focused on revealing the role of the press in the national-spiritual revival. In particular, the press, which came under the name of Jadid press and became a tribune of calling for national awakening, became a true herald of the ideas of independence, and these ideas have fulfilled a historical mission in the introducing in mind of the masses. It has been studied that nowadays, it is becoming more relevant to publish press articles about the Jadids and the Jadid press.

Keywords: Motherland, Jadids' liberation, independence, idea, thinker, self-awareness, movement, spirituality, social activity, nation, freedom.

The social-political views that were freely expressed in the territory of our country did not stop even in a certain difficult period of history. On the contrary, such a desire motivated the emergence of the idea of national independence in the minds of each of our compatriots. In the formation of such ideas, it is necessary to emphasize the Jadids movement that arose at the beginning of the XX century. The interest in the activities of Jadid thinkers in the press of the period of independence was a bright example of the respect of our people. In the struggle for the independence of the national state, special attention should be paid to the political analysis of the specific characteristics and conditions of the liberation movements.

It is assumed that the ideas of the Jadids' struggle for independence have been emerge. One of first conclusions of Behbudi was that social justice cannot be restored until the nation becomes free and establishes its own independent state. At the same time, such an idea formed the basis of the national independence movement. "In particular, our Jadids realized that the nation must be free and independent first of all in order for it to live and develop, and they paid special attention to awakening the people".¹

Jadids have focused on the development of spirituality in society. They needed to organize new schools, publish newspapers, textbooks and manuals, introduce new cultural and technological methods of the West and promote them to Turkestan, creating a national-worldwide education, renewing and

¹Kosimov B. National awakening: courage, enlightenment, dedication. Tashkent, Ma'naviyat, 2002, - p. 4.

enriching spiritual life, and creating a foundation for raising awareness of national identity. It should be recognized that such a political approach is a theoretical factor that directly serves the development of the foundations of a just state in society. It is known that “our ancestors were regularly engaged in political affairs, rights, national state, power issues. At the same time, school and education reform began. National press was launched. Theater appeared. New literature was formed, in a word, a new field of thought came. It was the realization of the identity of the nation and the ideology of independence. This situation, without a doubt, was unprecedented in the historical development of the nation in the following centuries. It was a sign of the beginning of a new stage in his life after a long period of stagnation”.²

The following articles from the press pages of the independence period can be proof of our opinion. B. Kosimov “The loud-voiced singer of the country and the nation” (Literature and art of Uzbekistan, December 5, 2003), N. Karimov “The last journey of Behbudi” (Society and management, 1998, Issue 1), B. Kosimov “Jadidism” (“Yoshlik”. 1990, No. 4), “Jadidism” (“Uzbek language and literature”. 1990, No. 2). “Jadidism” (“Saodat”. 1992, No. 12), B. Kosimov, H. Ismatullaev, U. Dolimov, Sh. Rizaev “Jadidism movement and literature of jadids” (round discussion, “Uzbek language and literature”. 1990, No. 4), B. Dustkoraev. The great figure of Turkestan Jadidism (“World literature” 1998), S. Holboev “Jadidism and independence” (Turkistan, June 5, 1993). Interest in the activities of Jadid thinkers in the press of the period of independence was a bright example of the respect of our people. There are a lot of materials, books, pamphlets and articles about the life and social activities of the Jadids during the period of independence, the development of the Uzbek national press.

In conclusion, the Jadid press appeared as a unique national idea and found its expression in the press of the independence period due to the fact that it stimulated the awakening of the nation. In fact, after Uzbekistan gained independence, restoring culture and spirituality, national values and traditions, returning to understanding the true history and identity became one of the priority directions of state policy in our country. In this sense, the first President of our country, Islam Karimov, firmly stated that “We consider the restoration of spiritual values to be a harmonic and natural process, which consists of the growth of the awareness of the national identity, the return to the spiritual roots of the nation and its roots”³

² Kosimov B. National awakening: courage, enlightenment, dedication. Tashkent, Ma'naviyat, 2002, - pp. 4-5.

³ Karimov I.A. On the way to security and sustainable development. Vol. 6. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 1998, - p 125.

It should be noted that the great interest in the work of Jadid thinkers in the press is a bright example of the respect of our people. There are many materials, books, pamphlets and articles related to the development of the Uzbek national press, the life and social activities of the Jadids during the period of independence, and we used them as much as possible and tried to analyze them only within the framework of our topic. We will not be wrong if we say that the study of materials related to the history of Jadid press, more precisely, the history of our national press, the scientific research of the activities of Jadid press served for the real spiritual revival and purification of our society, and the realization of the identity of the Uzbek people..

References:

1. Kosimov B. National awakening: courage, enlightenment, dedication. Tashkent, Ma'naviyat, 2002.
2. Karimov I.A. On the way to security and sustainable development. Vol. 6. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 1998.
3. Urinova B. The role of the periodical press in covering social-economic and cultural processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Monograph. Bukhara. 2004, p. 122
4. Urinova B. Independence as the Expression of Democratic National Ideas in the Jadids and the Jadid Press in Practice. AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. Volume 02, Issue 02, 2024pp. 539-542.
5. Urunova B. PRESS COVERAGE OF THE PROCESSES OF TRANSITION TO MARKET ECONOMY RELATIONS.2024.
6. Urinova B. Qalandarova F. The press as the creator of modern history. Scientific bulletin of Bukhara State University. 2020, No. 2. pp. 232-238.
7. Kalandarova F. Social Orphanhood: Causes and Consequences. Volume 02, Issue05, 2024. P 33-36.
8. Hojiyevich T.H., Bozorgul U.Z., Azamatovna K.F. The Life And The Scientific Heritage Of Mirza Sami //The journal of contemporary issues in business and government. – 2021. – Т. 27. – №. 1. – С. 212-218. 6.
9. Kalandarova F. A Portrait of Abdumalik Tora in Sami's Work. – 2023. 7. Kalandarova F. A. Quoting of quranic verses in historical works // "International scientific and practical conference" the time of scientific progress. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 19-26. 8.
10. Нафиддинова Х.Р., Каландарова Ф.А. Кушбеги Бухары-важный источник в изучении истории периода правления мангытов //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 7-2 (85). – С. 26-29. 9.

11. Каландарова Ф. А. Хронограммы в труде Мирзы Абдулазима Сами “Тарихи салатини Мангития” //Central Asian journal of social sciences and history. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 61-68.
12. Sobirovich, T. B. (2021). National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan. Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS), 5(3), 131-135.
13. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST), 7(1), 149-157.
14. Sobirovich, T. B. (2021). Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development. Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IJSR).
15. Sobirovich, T. B. (2020). Uzbekistan: from national revival to national progress. Modern scientific challenges and trends, (27), 5.
16. Turdiyev, B. (2021). Behbudi’s views on the spiritual renewal of society. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz), 5(5).
17. Sobirovich, T. B. (2020). The role of the strategy of spiritual renewal in the development of a democratic society in Uzbekistan. Lessons of Imam Bukhari, 2, 118-121.

